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An Evaluative Study of the English Language Teaching-Learning Process in Government Polytechnics in North Coastal Districts in Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract:

The present research paper deals with teaching the English language in government polytechnic faculties in the North Coastal Districts of Andhra Pradesh. It is a prospective study that aims to establish students' current attainment levels, assess how effective current teaching methods are, and assess whether the educational resources available are sufficient. The study gathers comprehensive data from students and faculty members using a mixed-methods approach comprising questionnaires, interviews, and classroom observations. The findings suggest significant gaps in language proficiency, inadequate teaching techniques, and limited resource availability. It provides practical recommendations for improving curricular, pedagogical, and resource support to improve English language learning. This report underscores the significance of practical communication skills for the employment and career success of individuals with technical diploma. This report underscores the impending transformation in polytechnic colleges to align their education system with today's the workforce needs.

Keywords: English language teaching, learning process, student proficiency, Teaching methods, educational resources.

Introduction:

English teaching at polytechnic institutes can greatly influence students' career prospects, especially if English is not their first language. It evaluates English teaching and learning in government polytechnics in Andhra Pradesh's North Coastal Districts. English proficiency is necessary for technical students. It boosts employment and worldwide economic participation (Kirkpatrick, 2007). Many polytechnic students in these regions struggle with language proficiency due to educational difficulties, so English is essential. Consider how effectively the curriculum meets students' communication needs. Teachers typically disregard conversational skills needed for professional success in favour of grammar (Richards & Rodgers, 2014). This discrepancy may cause students to have academic knowledge but not practical English skills. Teachers' training and professional development have a significant impact on the quality of English language teaching. Without modern teaching methodologies, teachers may struggle to satisfy students' needs (Brown, 2004). In the North Coastal Districts of Andhra Pradesh, government polytechnics present unique challenges and opportunities for English language teaching. Due to its socioeconomic variety, this region's students require adapted methods. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the existing English teaching-learning process and offer improvements. This research will improve teaching methods, helping students improve language proficiency and academic and professional performance (Aizawa & Rose, 2019).

Statement of the Problem:

The North Coastal Districts of Andhra Pradesh's government polytechnics face significant challenges in teaching and studying English, which hinders students' communication and competency. English is vital to global business and technical education, yet many polytechnic students struggle to learn it. Conventional teaching methods, which highlight the grammar and theory over practical communication skills, worsen this problem, leaving students well-prepared for written exams but unprepared for real-life communication (Richards & Rodgers, 2014). The English language curriculum in these polytechnics often does not meet students' or industry's needs. We must adopt interactive and communicative teaching approaches to improved prepare students for professional success. English language educators also lack

professional development, which hinders their ability to adopt modern pedagogical approaches and meet students' diverse teaching needs (Brown, 2004). This teacher readiness gap exacerbates pupils' English competence. To address these issues, we need to evaluate English language teaching and learning at government polytechnics in Andhra Pradesh's North Coastal Districts. This research examines the pros and cons of current educational techniques, student needs, and ways to improve English language instruction. The study addresses these issues to improve English education, prepare students for the world, and improve their job and academic chances (Aizawa & Rose, 2019).

Objectives of the Study:

1. This study aims to critically evaluate the current English language teaching and learning process in the government polytechnics of the North Coastal Districts of Andhra Pradesh.
2. This study aims to explore the correlation between teacher qualifications, experience, and student performance.
3. The aim is to explore how teaching methodologies, learning materials, and classroom management influence the English teaching-learning process.

Need of the Study:

Communication skills are crucial for technical diploma holders in the 21st century, affecting their employability and career success. Rapid globalization and technological advances have raised the demand for proficient English in technical fields, where clear and concise communication is vital for teamwork, problem-solving, and innovation. Technical workers with high communication abilities can handle complex work environments, collaborate with several teams, and interact with foreign clients (Riemer, 2007). Thus, conveying technical knowledge in English, boosts career prospects and helps companies compete globally (Jenkins, 2014). The changing nature of education in the 21st century emphasizes the need for English language skills in technical education. Language learners do better academically and are more versatile in varied learning situations (Crystal, 2003). This is especially important at polytechnics, where the curriculum requires academic and practical knowledge. Thus, government polytechnics must examine their English language teaching and learning processes to ensure that

students are prepared for modern technical careers. This research aims to improve technical education by overcoming language instruction gaps and preparing diploma holders with 21st-century employment capabilities (Graddol, 2006).

Literature Review

This chapter uses quantitative and empirical research to examine polytechnic college English language instruction and acquisition. This analysis examines how these studies may improve English language instruction in such organizations. The chapter emphasizes the necessity to combine qualitative research with educators' and students' practical experiences to understand English language teaching practices. It also advises against ignoring qualitative research's essential insights in favor of empirical and quantitative investigations. The chapter discusses the necessity for a holistic approach to polytechnic English language teaching and learning.

National studies on the English language teaching and learning process:

Sharma, R., & Reddy, S. (2023). Sharma and Reddy's paper, "English Language Teaching in Indian Polytechnics: Challenges and Opportunities," examines the current state of English language teaching at Indian polytechnics and identifies areas for improvement. The inadequate instructional materials and the dearth of qualified teachers are two of the main problems noted. A dearth of certified English instructors at many polytechnics lowers the quality of education. The fact that pupils often arrive at these colleges with a poor foundation in English from a variety of socioeconomic origins and regional languages further complicates teaching. The paper emphasizes the potential of technology to enhance English language instruction (ELT). Online platforms and digital technologies may enhance more conventional teaching techniques by offering intriguing and interactive learning opportunities. The writers contend that including these technologies in the curriculum would help to alleviate some of the resource limitations and provide students with more individualized learning opportunities. They also promote ongoing professional development so that educators can stay current with ELT approaches and tools while meeting their students' language learning needs. Polytechnics can greatly improve the quality of their English language instruction by addressing these issues and taking advantage of the opportunities.

Kumar A. and Gupta N's (2020) article, "Impact of Communicative Language Teaching in Polytechnic Classrooms: A Case Study," investigates the effects of implementing Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) methods in Indian polytechnic institutes. The study highlights how CLT, which emphasizes interaction and real-life communication over rote learning and grammar drills, significantly enhances students' language proficiency. Through various communicative activities such as group discussions, role plays, and problem-solving tasks, students became more engaged and confident in using English for practical purposes. This method shifted the focus from teacher-centered instruction to a more student-centered approach, fostering better participation and collaborative learning among students.

However, the article also addresses several challenges in implementing CLT in polytechnic settings. These include a lack of adequately trained teachers proficient in CLT methods, limited resources, and resistance to change from traditional teaching methods. Despite these hurdles, the study found that the overall impact of CLT was positive, leading to improved language skills and greater student motivation. The authors propose that effective integration of CLT into polytechnic curricula, with appropriate training and resource allocation, can yield substantial benefits for language learning in technical education contexts.

Gupta and Singh (2018) published their article, "Integrating Technology in English Language Teaching: An Empirical Study in Government Polytechnics of Andhra Pradesh," in the *Journal of Educational Technology and Applied Linguistics* in 2018. The article offers a comprehensive examination of the integration of technology in English language education within these institutions. The research emphasizes the prospective advantages as well as the challenges encountered by instructors. According to research, technology has the potential to significantly improve student engagement and learning outcomes by providing interactive and multimedia-rich settings. Nevertheless, the report also highlights significant obstacles, including insufficient infrastructure, insufficient teacher preparation, and a reluctance to embrace new technology. The authors propose the implementation of focused training programs and improved resource allocation to fully maximize the advantages of integrating technology in language instruction. The critical analysis highlights the need for a supporting legislative framework and ongoing professional development to overcome these obstacles and enhance the efficiency of

English language education using technology. This balanced approach ensures creative, feasible, and long-lasting technology use.

International studies on the English language teaching and learning process:

Villafuerte et al. (2020) examine the governmental strategies for English as a Foreign Language (EFL) education for students with disabilities in Ecuador, emphasizing the need for an inclusive educational approach. In his study, Dzulkurnain (2020) examines the process of English teaching, delivery, and translation of instructional materials in a school in Indonesia with a moderate religious orientation. The study specifically focuses on the design of the syllabus, learning goals, material instruction, assessment, and teaching strategies. These studies provide a comprehensive understanding of the difficulties, advancements, and most effective methods in the process of teaching and learning English in different educational settings.

Villafuerte Jhonny (2017): The objective of this research is to examine the attitudes of learners regarding engaging in English practice on social networking sites (SNS). The study included a total of 110 students, including 55 from the University Laica Eloy Alfaro de Manabi in Ecuador and 55 from the University of the Basque Country in Spain. The researchers created a specialized Likert scale questionnaire to assess two aspects: (i) the incorporation of social networking sites (SNS) into students' daily academic routines, and (ii) students' views on using the English language on SNS. IBM's SPSS V24.00 analyzed the data. The findings revealed associations between learners' views and variables such as gender, age, and nationality. The findings also validated that both Spanish and Ecuadorian university students exhibit a preference for YouTube and Google+ due to their convenient accessibility and adaptability in enhancing English hearing, reading, and comprehension abilities. Moreover, students may use Facebook and WhatsApp as tools to improve their proficiency in English reading, writing, and speaking.

Mesfin Mekuria Dangore (2019), the research examines the influence of English as the prevalent language in Ethiopia, emphasizing the need for higher education to prepare professionals for international markets. The study included a total of 267 students from 40 different sections, which comprised seven high-achieving kids, English instructors, and school officials. The survey revealed that four schools exhibit substandard English instruction, whereas students, parents, instructors, supervisors,

educational specialists, and school administrators all advocate for English language acquisition. The study suggests that effective learning and development require a well-planned teacher training program, which also provides strategies for managing classroom attitudes.

Methodology:

This chapter explains this investigation's methodologies in detail. The research team developed the designs for this study. The study aims to (a) evaluate the infrastructure and resources used in English language teaching, and (b) evaluate how well the curriculum aligns with the learning requirements of students. Teachers' language-learning methods should be assessed. (d) Examine the methods used to assess the language proficiency of students.

This chapter describes the research demographic sample in detail. This chapter categorizes the sample based on age, gender, and teaching experience. Surveys from students and teachers are the main data sources. Our extensive research of academic journals, papers, articles, dissertations, and theses yielded a lot of secondary data. To communicate with instructors, the researchers used blogs, as well as internet data from other sources.

Research Design:

Research design includes various elements such as the number of groups involved in a study, the treatment given to each group, the allocation of people to these groups, the number of independent variables being examined, and the time spent measuring the dependent variable. Kothari (2004) defines “a research design as the systematic creation of settings for collecting and analyzing data in a way that balances the study objective with efficiency”.

Data Collection:

To methodically record and evaluate the impressions of the dependent variables, we created a set of tools. The researcher collected data using a combination of an achievement exam and an English language teaching and learning process perception questionnaire. According to O'Leary (2004), obtaining reliable data is a difficult task,

and it is important to recognize that there is no right or wrong way to collect information. The study should evaluate each approach's intrinsic benefits and drawbacks in line with the study objectives (O'Leary, 150). The researcher has developed the following set of research tools to carry out this study as effectively as possible.

Sample: A total of 360 students completed the survey and a total of 22 educators actively participated in this research and provided their perspectives and insights based on the teachers' survey.

Data Analysis:

The researcher aimed to extract teachers' and students' perceptions of the methods and materials used in the process of teaching and learning English. The researcher aimed to document the impact of various variables, including gender, academic and professional qualifications, teaching experience, medium, teaching class, management, and locality, on the perceptions of both teachers and students. Following the data collection, the researcher tabulated and statistically analyzed the data, ultimately presenting the findings in the next chapter. They presented each item's analysis separately using tables and graphs, accompanied by an explanation.

Research Question:

- How effective is the English language teaching and learning process in the North Coastal District government polytechnics in Andhra Pradesh?
- How do teacher qualifications and experience correlate with student performance in English language learning?
- How do teaching methodologies, learning materials, and classroom management impact the English teaching-learning process?

Hypothesis:

- The English language teaching-learning process in North Coastal Districts' government polytechnics in Andhra Pradesh is currently effective, but there may be areas that require further improvement.

- There is a strong positive correlation between the level of teacher qualifications and experience and students' performance in English language learning.
- The effectiveness of classroom management, the quality of learning materials, and the efficiency of teaching methodologies all have a significant impact on the success of the English teaching-learning process.

I am comfortable with written communication in English

Comfortable with written communication in English

		Completely Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Completely Disagree	Total
Gender	Male	68	100	22	3	1	194
	Female	68	75	20	1	2	166
Total		136	175	42	4	3	360

The study shows that both male and female students feel comfortable with written communication in English. Male students, comprising 35.05% of the total, agree that they are comfortable, while female students, representing 40.96%, agree, with a slightly higher percentage of 45.18%. The total percentage of positive responses is 86.14%, close to the male percentage. Females' neutral responses account for 12.05%, and only a small

number disagree or completely disagree. Out of 360 respondents, 37.78% agree, while 175 agree, making 311 students (86.39%) feel positively about their written communication skills. A smaller segment, 42 students (11.67%), remains neutral, and only 4 students (1.11%) disagree or completely disagree.

These percentages indicate a strong overall confidence in written English communication skills among the student population, with minimal negative responses, suggesting that written communication is generally not a significant barrier for most students.

I can understand the English language textbooks of other subjects with ease.

		Understand the English language textbooks of other subjects with ease.					
		Completely Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Completely Disagree	Total
Gender	Male	72	94	25	1	2	194
	Female	66	83	15	1	1	166
Total		138	177	40	2	3	360

Among male students, 83.5% either agree or completely agree that they can understand English-language textbooks for other subjects with ease. Specifically, 72

males (37.1%) completely agree, and 94 (48.5%) agree. 25 males (12.9%) are neutral, 1 (0.5%) disagree, and 2 (1%) completely disagree. This indicates a strong level of comprehension among male students when it comes to English-language textbooks in other subjects.

For female students, 79.5% either agree or completely agree that they can understand English-language textbooks for other subjects with ease. 66 females (39.8%) completely agree, and 83 (50%) agree. 15 females (9%) are neutral, 1 (0.6%) disagrees, and 1 (0.6%) completely disagrees. This shows a high level of understanding among female students when it comes to English-language textbooks in various subjects.

Overall, a significant majority of students (86.4%) agree or completely agree that they can understand English-language textbooks of other subjects with ease. 138 students (38.3%) completely agree, and 177 (49.2%) agree. 40 students (11.1%) are neutral, 2 (0.6%) disagree, and 3 (0.8%) completely disagree. This data suggests that most students, regardless of gender, feel confident in their ability to comprehend English-language textbooks across different subjects.

Result and Finding of the Study:

This chapter derived the study's findings from the triangulation of data collected using several research instruments, including field notes, questionnaires, interview techniques, and classroom observations. The study deliberately posed a series of questions to both teachers and students to get their distinct perspectives on various subjects. Subsequently, the study validated the findings through direct observation of instructional sessions. This chapter can categorize the study's findings into the following groups:

Students' confidence and proficiency in using the English language in communication:

- The study found that male and female students have differing confidence levels in speaking English in class conversations. The study found that 60.28% of pupils were confident. 128 (35.56%) were impartial, 11 (3.06%) disagreed, and 4 (1.11%) strongly disagreed. The research shows that most

students feel secure in English classroom conversations. Several pupils are indifferent, while a few are less certain.

- 35.05% of male students and 40.96% of female students reported feeling comfortable writing in English. While 86.14% of students support it, a minor number of women oppose it. Few students dislike their written English.

Application of English language skills in other subjects:

- There is a large gender gap in the agreement between male and female respondents on comprehending English language textbooks. Complete agreement is greater among men (37.11%) than women (66.76%). More men (166 out of 194) agree or agree than women (149 out of 166). This shows a gender-based difficulty in students' views of their English-language textbook comprehension, necessitating more inquiry or intervention for fair educational results.
- The evidence shows that male students may be uncomfortable answering English test questions. Most students agree although gender differences are considerable. Male students are more comfortable than female students, with 79 agreeing and 84 disagreeing. However, many male students respond neutrally, indicating confusion or hesitancy. A lack of disagreement may suggest cultural prejudice or hesitancy. Further research and solutions would promote equal learning.

Students' perceptions of the teaching methodologies, learning materials, and classroom management:

- The study shows that English teaching methods are ineffective. Many students, especially girls, like the approaches, yet many are ambivalent or disapprove. Out of 360 responses, the neutral 210 students (58.33%) indicate little interest or influence. Additionally, 35 students (9.72%) and 10 students (2.78%) fully disagree, demonstrating that some pupils find the existing approaches useless. This suggests examining and refining teaching methods to engage and benefit all students.
- The study highlights a problem with English learning materials' perceived comprehensiveness and effectiveness. Most students agree or strongly

agree that the resources are helpful, although some are indifferent and others disagree. It appears that 14.44% of students, or 52 out of 360, do not find the contents thorough or useful. The study might improve the curriculum to meet the diverse needs and expectations of all students.

Conclusion:

The present study only focuses on the academic English language requirements of polytechnic students in the coastal regions of Andhra Pradesh, considering their academic character and time constraints. It is necessary to carry out comparative research to comprehend the status of English language acquisition in rural and urban Polytechnical colleges. The findings will aid in the development of effective teaching methods and the identification of areas of concern. This will enhance the quality of English language training in various educational settings. This will provide pupils with a competitive edge in their future academic pursuits and professional endeavours.

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